

Optimization Of Mycelial Growth And Exopolysaccharide Production By *Calocybe Indica* Using Response Surface Methodology

K. T. K. Anandapandian¹ and M. Eyini²

¹ Department of Microbiology, Sokoto state University, Sokoto, Nigeria

² Research centre in Botany, Thiagarajar College (Autonomous), Madurai, Tamilnadu, India.

*Corresponding author: K.T K. Anandapandian
Professor,
Department of Microbiology,
Sokoto state University,
Along Airport road, Sokoto, Nigeria.
Contact no: +2348089797483
E-mail: anandapandian@yahoo.com

Received: May 12, 2014, Accepted: June 2, 2014, Published: June 3, 2014.

ABSTRACT

Response surface methodology (statistical analysis) was applied to optimize the medium composition for the mycelial growth and exopolysaccharide production by *Calocybe indica* in submerged cultures. Firstly, three significant factors (Glucose, peptone and incubation days) on mycelial growth (g/50ml) and exopolysaccharide yield (mg/50ml) were obtained using central composite design. Subsequently, in order to study the mutual interactions between variables, the effects of these factors were further investigated using three-factor, central composite design and the optimal composition for mycelial growth was (in g/L): Glucose 10, peptone 5, and Incubation was 28 days also, the optimal composition for maximum exopolysaccharide production in *Calocybe indica* was (in g/L): Glucose 15, peptone 2.5, and incubation 21 days under the optimized medium, respectively.

Keyword: *Calocybe indica*, optimization, Response surface methodology, Exopolysaccharide, statistical analysis.

INTRODUCTION

Extra cellular polymeric substances (EPS) are a complex mixture of macromolecular polyelectrolytes including polysaccharides, proteins, and nucleic acids, each comprising variable molecular mass and structural properties. During the past three decades, many polysaccharides-protein complexes have been isolated from fungi, algae, lichens and plants (Ooi and Liu, 2000) [5]. Furthermore, most of them which have various physiological activities were originated from fungi especially mushrooms (Kim *et al.*, 2002)[2]. Mushrooms comprise a vast and yet largely untapped source of powerful new pharmaceutical products. In particular and most importantly for modern medicine, they represent an unlimited source of polysaccharides with antitumour and immunostimulating properties.

Many basidiomycetes contain biologically active polysaccharides. EPS are distributed between the cell surface (i.e., capsular or hyphal-bound EPS), the aqueous phase (i.e., slime or free EPS), or occur as a hydrated matrix in biofilm (biofilm EPS), with a composition that depends on growth phase and solution chemistry. This mixture mediates cell adhesion through interfacial processes including covalent or ionic bonding, dipole interactions, steric interactions, and hydrophobic association. Recently

exopolysaccharides are considered as a type of mushroom nutraceutical compounds having both nutritional and medicinal effects. They are linked with the immune enhancing property of edible mushrooms supporting the concept of "food as medicine".

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Organism

Pure culture of the milky mushroom strain *Calocybe indica* P&C (APK 2) was obtained from Tamilnadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu, India. The cultures of both the mushrooms were maintained on Malt extract agar (MEA) medium. Petriplates (9 cm diameter) containing MEA medium were inoculated individually with a mycelial agar plug (7 mm diameter) from the margin of a young, actively growing 7 days old colony of *Calocybe indica*. The plates were incubated at $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ in the dark for 8 to 10 days until mycelial growth covered the entire surface of the MEA plates. The cultures were maintained on MEA slopes at 5°C and regularly sub cultured every month. Once in three months both the cultures were revived through the mother stock culture prepared from the respective fruiting bodies.

Optimization of growth conditions for biomass and EPS production

Production of biomass of *C. indica* using Waksman medium was low in classical optimization method. Hence medium optimization was attempted using central composite design by changing the Waksman medium composition as per the run order of CCD.

Response-Surface Methodology (RSM) was used to investigate the influence of different carbon and nitrogen sources, on the yields of biomass and extracellular EPS by *C. indica*. Central composite design with 3 factors at three levels including three replicates at the center point was used for fitting data on a second-order polynomial model (Li *et al.*, 2007; Praveen *et al.*, 2008)[3,6]. The modeling and statistical analysis were performed using Design Expert, version 7.01 software (Stat –Ease Corp. Minneapolis, Minn.). The mathematical method describing the relationships between the process responses (the yield of mycelial biomass or EPS) and the medium contents was developed. The yield of mycelial biomass or EPS by *C. indica* was multiply regressed with respect to the medium contents by the least squares method as follows:

$$Y = A_0 + \sum A_i X_i + \sum A_{ii} X_i^2 + \sum A_{ij} X_i X_j$$

Where Y is the predicted response variable; A₀, A_i, A_{ii}, A_{ij} are regression coefficients of the model and X_i, X_j (i = 1, 3; j = 1, 3, I... j) represent the independent variables (medium components) in form of coded or real values. The accuracy and general ability of the above polynomial model were evaluated by coefficient of determination (R²).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Optimization of biomass production by Response surface methodology.

Biomass production by *C. indica* was optimized using central composite design and response surface methodology in the cubic model, using Design Expert, version 7.01 software (Stat –Ease Corp. Minneapolis, Minn.). Biomass production of this mushroom was optimized by varying the concentrations of the medium components especially the carbon, nitrogen sources and the incubation time, at controlled temperature without taking into account the effect of change in pH during cultivation. The optimization of conditions was performed using CCD with fixed central points of glucose, 10g/l, peptone, 5g/l and incubation time, 14 days. The coded values and the levels of variables used in the CCD design was shown in the Table 1.

Response surface methodology helps in evaluation of relationship between the dependent (biomass yield) variable and independent variables (media components/incubation period). Observed and predicted values of the biomass yield are shown in Table 3. The accuracy of the model can be seen by the difference between observed and predicted values. The co-efficient and the analysis of variance are presented in Table 2 Fitness of the model explained by the value of the determination co-efficient (R²). In the present study R² comes out to be 0.99 for *C. indica*. Higher value of adjusted co-efficient of determination adjusted R² = 0.99 for *C. indica* indicates high significance of the model. The application of RSM yielded following the order polynomial equation.

$$Y_1 = +5.31 + 1.07 * A + 0.045 * B + 2.36 * C - 0.094 * A * B + 0.82 * A * C + 0.076 * B * C - 0.62 * A^2 - 0.19 * B^2 - 0.64 * C^2 - 0.13 * A * B * C + 0.099 * A^2 * B + 0.53 * A^2 * C - 0.11 * A * B^2$$

$$Y_2 = +3.47 + 0.67 * A + 0.46 * B + 2.33 * C - 0.31 * A * B + 0.28 * A * C + 0.49 * B * C - 0.32 * A^2 + 0.097 * B^2 + 0.19 * C^2 - 0.42 * A * B * C + 0.18 * A^2 * B + 0.050 * A^2 * C - 0.061 * A * B^2$$

Where Y₁ or Y₂ is the response i.e., logarithmic value of biomass production (g/50ml) and A, B and C are the uncoded values of the test variables peptone, glucose and incubation period. Model co-efficients of variation are shown in Fig.1. Response surface and contour figures, obtained by the analysis of the experimental data of CCD, showed a relationship between two variables at a time, while maintaining the third variable at fixed level (zero, coded units). These figures are helpful in understanding both linear and interaction effect of the two variables. Fig 1a shows the interaction of glucose and incubation period. Fig.1b shows that 5-7.5 g peptone and 10-15g/l glucose gave high biomass yield. Fig.1c shows that biomass yield was maximum at 21 and 28 days of incubation and peptone concentration 2.5- 7.5g/l was equally effective in increasing the biomass of *C. indica*

The ANOVA for the results indicated that the cubic regression to produce the third order was significant. The lack of fit test was insignificant and model did not explain 15.83% and 6.04% of total variations for *C. indica*. Regression equation (Y₁ or Y₂) for the levels of biomass production as functions of glucose concentration (A), peptone concentration (B) and Incubation time(C) suggested that all the three factors influenced biomass production by the organism. The ANOVA analysis of biomass production by *C. indica* showed that P>F value was 0.0001 and the model was significant for biomass production response for the organism. The precision of signal to noise ratio which was 44.25 for the biomass production by *C. indica* indicates the adequate signal.

The results predicted the maximum biomass production 8.22g by *indica* in 50 ml of liquid nutrient medium under the experimental conditions of glucose concentration 10g/l, peptone concentration 5g/l and incubation time 28 days (Table.3 Run 17). All the three linear co-efficients glucose concentration, peptone concentration, Incubation time and quadratic terms (AB, AC, BC) and squared terms(A², C²) and ABC were significant, indicating biomass production depended on all the three factors selected and optimum conditions for maximum biomass production was determined by three dimensional response surface plots.

Optimization of EPS production by Response surface methodology.

Exopolysaccharide production by *C. indica* was optimized using central composite design and response surface methodology in the cubic model, using Design Expert, version 7.01 software (Stat –Ease Corp. Minneapolis, Minn.). EPS production by this mushroom was optimized by varying concentration of the medium components especially the carbon, nitrogen sources and the incubation time, at controlled temperature without taking into account the effect of change in pH during cultivation. The optimization of conditions was performed using CCD with fixed central points of glucose, 10g/l, peptone, 5g/l and incubation time, 14 days. The coded values and the levels of variables used in the CCD design was shown in Table 1

Response surface methodology helps in evaluation of relationship between the dependent (EPS yield) variable and independent variables (media components / incubation period). Observed and predicted values of the biomass yield are shown in

Table 4. The accuracy of the model can be seen by the difference between observed and predicted values. The co-efficient and the analysis of variance are presented in Table 2. Fitness of the model explained by the value of the determination co-efficient (R^2). In the present study R^2 comes out to be 0.99 for *C. indica*. Higher value of adjusted co-efficient of determination adjusted $R^2 = 0.99$ for *C. indica* indicates high significance of the model. The application of RSM yielded following third order polynomial equation.

$$Y_3 = +2.12 + 0.40 * A - 0.31 * B + 0.28 * C + 0.094 * A * B + 0.31 * A * C + 0.19 * B * C + 0.036 * A^2 - 0.054 * B^2 - 0.30 * C^2 - 0.17 * A * B * C + 0.51 * A^2 * B + 0.62 * A^2 * C + 0.17 * A * B^2$$

$$Y_4 = +1.20 + 0.19 * A + 0.089 * B + 0.32 * C - 0.21 * A * B - 0.094 * A * C - 0.011 * B * C - 0.024 * A^2 + 0.056 * B^2 - 0.17 * C^2 - 0.35 * A * B * C + 0.027 * A^2 * B + 0.32 * A^2 * C - 9.496 - 003 * A * B^2$$

Where Y_3 or Y_4 is the response ie., logarithmic value of biomass production (g/l) and A,B and C are the uncoded values of the test variables peptone, glucose and incubation period. Model co-efficients of variation are shown in Fig.2. Response surface and contour figures, obtained by the analysis of the experimental data of CCD, show a relationship between two variables at a time, maintaining third variable at the fixed level (zero, coded units). These figures are helpful in understanding both linear and interaction effect of the two variables. Fig 2a shows the interaction

of glucose and incubation period. As glucose concentration increased between 10 and 15% at higher incubation period (28 days), EPS production of *P. pulmonarius* also increased. Fig.2b shows that 7.5-10 g peptone and 15-20g/l glucose gave high EPS yield. Fig.2c shows that EPS yield was maximum, at 21 and 28 days of incubation and peptone concentration 2.5-7.5g/l was equally effective in increasing the EPS of *C. indica*.

The ANOVA for the results indicated that the cubic regression to produce the third order was significant. The lack of fit test was insignificant and model did not explain 2.89% of total variations for *C. indica*. Regression equation for the levels of EPS production (Y_3 or Y_4) as functions of glucose concentration (A), peptone concentration (B) and Incubation time(C) suggested that all the three factors influenced EPS production by the organism. The ANOVA analysis of EPS production by *C. indica* showed that $P>F$ value was 0.0001 and the model was significant for biomass production response for the organism. The precision of signal to noise ratio which was 2.89 for the EPS production by *C. indica* indicates the adequate signal.

The results predicted the maximum EPS production 22.8mg by *C. indica* under the experimental conditions of glucose concentration 15g/l, peptone concentration 5g/l or 2.5g/l and incubation time 21 days (Table 4 Run 2). All the three linear co-efficients glucose concentration, peptone concentration, incubation time, quadratic terms (AB, AC, BC), squared terms (A^2, C^2) and ABC were significant, indicating EPS production depended on all the three factors selected.

Table.1. Levels of process variables used in central composite design

Variables	Coded levels				
	-2	-1	0	+1	+2
Glucose (g/l)	2.5	5	10	15	20
Peptone (g/l)	1.25	2.5	5	7.5	10
Incubation time (Days)	3	7	14	21	28

Table.2. ANOVA for model used for mycelial growth (biomass production) and EPS production by *C.indica*

Terms	<i>Calocybe indica</i>	
	Biomass	EPS
F-value	171.24	469.66
P>F	0.0001	0.0001
Mean	3.39	1.11
R^2	0.99	0.99
Adjusted R^2	0.99	0.99
Co-efficient of variance	6.04	2.89
Adequate precision	44.24	76.59

--	--	--

Table.3. Central composite design and the mycelial growth (biomass) response obtained from the culture trials of *C. indica* in Waksman medium

Run order	Block	Coded levels			Response	
					Biomass(g/50ml)	
		<i>Calocybe indica</i>				
		Glucose	Peptone	Incubation	Observed	Predicted
1	1	-1	+1	+1	6.50	6.55
2	1	+1	-1	+1	6.01	6.23
3	1	-1	-1	-1	0.38	0.45
4	1	0	0	0	3.33	3.25
5	1	0	0	0	3.25	3.45
6	1	-1	-1	+1	2.76	3.12
7	1	+1	-1	-1	0.83	0.90
8	1	+1	+1	-1	1.35	1.55
9	1	+1	+1	+1	6.80	7.10
10	1	0	0	0	3.15	3.22
11	2	-1	+1	-1	0.46	0.54
12	2	0	0	0	3.30	3.35
13	2	0	-2	0	3.33	3.40
14	2	+2	0	0	4.01	4.13
15	2	-2	0	0	1.75	1.85
16	2	0	0	-2	0.38	0.50
17	2	0	0	+2	8.22	8.25
18	2	0	+2	0	4.82	5.10
19	2	0	0	0	3.28	3.35
20	2	0	0	0	3.32	3.41

Table.4. Central composite design and exopolysaccharide production response obtained from the culture trials of *C. indica*

Run order	Block	Coded levels			Response	
					EPS (mg/50ml)	
		<i>Calocybe indica</i>				
		Glucose	Peptone	Incubation	Observed	Predicted
1	1	-1	+1	+1	22.5	21.4
2	1	+1	-1	+1	22.8	23.0
3	1	-1	-1	-1	1.7	2.5
4	1	0	0	0	12.4	12.8
5	1	0	0	0	12.1	12.5
6	1	-1	-1	+1	9.6	9.0
7	1	+1	-1	-1	4.5	5.5
8	1	+1	+1	-1	9.8	9.5
9	1	+1	+1	+1	13.5	15.0
10	1	0	0	0	12.0	15
11	2	-1	+1	-1	14.5	15.7
12	2	0	0	0	1.5	2.4
13	2	0	-2	0	12.1	12.5
14	2	+2	0	0	12.0	12.7
15	2	-2	0	0	14.5	15.8

16	2	0	0	-2	8.0	9.1
17	2	0	0	+2	1.9	2.5
18	2	0	+2	0	15.0	17.2
19	2	0	0	0	12.8	13.5
20	2	0	0	0	13.0	14.8

Fig 1 (a, b, c) . Response surface plots of interaction between process variables in mycelial growth (biomass production) by *C.indica* in Waksman medium

Fig 2 (a, b, c). Response surface plots of interaction between process variables in EPS production by *C.indica* in Waksman medium

eps
 ● Design points above predicted value
 ○ Design points below predicted value
 2.28
 0.15
 X1 = B: peptone
 X2 = C: incubation time
 Actual Factor
 A: glucose = 0.00

DISCUSSION

The conventional method of optimization which involves varying one parameter at a time and keeping the others at a fixed level is time consuming and expensive when a large number of variables are evaluated at different levels. Statistical methods like, Response Surface Methodology (RSM) fairly reduces the total number of experiments required (only 20) and also manifests any possible interaction effect between constituents (Praveen *et al.*, 2008)[6].

Optimization studies conducted in the present investigation for finding out the interaction between the medium components glucose and peptone and the incubation time revealed that maximum biomass production at 28 days of incubation, while maximum EPS production occurred after 21 days in *C. indica*. There was no correlation between biomass and EPS production after 14th day of incubation. Similar results were expressed by Wagner *et al.* (2003)[10].

There was no interaction between incubation time and peptone concentration. Increasing peptone concentration between 5 and 10g/l significantly increased the *C. indica* biomass production after 21st day of incubation. In *C. indica* biomass production peptone concentration above 7.5g/l could only effect maximal biomass production. For high EPS production, *C. indica* required above 15g/l glucose. Increasing peptone concentration between 5 and 10g/l had a significant effect on the EPS production by *C. indica*. EPS production and biomass yield was found to vary with respect to the mushroom species, the medium components and incubation time. Similar results were reported by Yang and Liau. (1998)[9] who obtained maximum polysaccharide production (1600 mg/l) in *G. lucidum* in a glucose ammonium chloride medium. Similar results were reported by Huang *et al.* (2007)[1] who obtained the maximal yield of *Hericieum erinaceus* mycelial biomass and its exopolymer yield at he same concentration of corn flour(30g/l) and glucose (10g/l) suggested that biomass and EPS production were influenced by the same range of concentration of carbon and nitrogen sources.

In contrast to our results, Kim *et al.* (2002)[2] achieved a relatively higher exopolymer production by *Ganoderma lucidum* and *Phellinus linteus* in starch rich potato malt medium than in mushroom complete medium containing higher glucose concentration. It is interesting to note that EPS production is not consistent with mycelial growth of *P. pulmonarius* which is often the case in fermentation kinetics of higher fungi. Kim *et al.* (2002) have reported similar results for *P. lentius*. These results indicated that the carbon source could be utilized for EPS production as

good mycelial growth seems not to be a determining factor for high yield of EPS in *P. pulmonarius*. Similar results were observed in *Lentinus* (Lee *et al.*, 1995)[3] and *G. lucidum* (Sone *et al.*, 1985)[8]. However Park *et al.* (1994)[7] reported that mycelial growth was closely related to the protein bound polysaccharide production in *C. versicolor*. The results of EPS and biomass production by *C. indica* as observed in the present investigation agree with this report.

REFERENCE:

- Huang, D. F. C, Y. Li, Z. Zhang, J. Zhao X. Han, X. Xiao, J. Qian, Q. Wu and G. Guan, 2007. Nutritional requirements for the mycelial biomass and exopolymer production by *Hericieum erinaceus* CZ-2. *Food Technol. Biotechnol.*, 45: 389-395.
- Kim, S. W, H. J. Hwang, C. P. Xu, Y. S. Na, S. K. Song and J. W. Yun, 2002. Influence of nutritional conditions on the mycelial growth and exopolysaccharide production in *Paecilomyces sinclairii*, *Lett. Appl. Microbiol.*, 34: 389-393.
- Li, J, C. Ma, Y. Ma, Y. Li, W. Zhou and P. Xu, 2007. Medium optimization by combination of response surface methodology and desirability function: an application in glutamine production. *Appl Microbiol Biotechnol.*, 74: 563-571.
- Lee, J. H, S. M. Cho, K. S. Ko and I. D. Yoo, 1995. Effect of cultural conditions on polysaccharide production and its monosaccharide composition in *Phellinus linteus* L13202. *Korean J.Mycol.*, 23: 325-331.
- Ooi, V. E and F. Liu, 2000. Immunomodulation and anti-cancer activity of polysaccharide-protein complexes. *Cur.Med.Chem.*, 7: 715-729.
- Praveen, V, D. Tripathi, C. K. M. Tripathi and V. Bihari, 2008. Nutritional regulation of actinomycin-D production by a new isolate of *Streptomyces sinderensis* using statistical methods. *Indian J.Exp.Biol.*, 46: 138-144.
- Park, K. S, S. Park, I. C. Jung, H. C. Ha, S. H. Kim and J. S. Lee, 1994. Production of protein bound polysaccharides by solid state fermentation of *Coriolus versicolor*. *Korean J Microbiol.*, 22: 184-189.
- Sone, Y, R. Okuda, N. Wada, E. Kishida and A. Misaki, 1985. Structure and antitumour activities of the polysaccharide isolated from fruiting body and the growing culture of mycelium of *Ganoderma lucidum*. *Agri and Biol.Chem.*, 49: 2641-2653.

9. Yang, F. C and C. B. Liau, 1998. The influence of environmental conditions on polysaccharide formation by *Ganoderma lucidum* in submerged cultures. *Process. Biochem.*, 33: 547-553.
10. Wagner, R, D. A. Mitchell, G. L. Sasaki, M. A. L. De. A. Amazonas and M. Berovic, 2003. Current techniques for the cultivation of for the production of Biomass, Ganoderic acid and polysaccharides. *Food.Technol.Biotechnol.*, 41: 371-382.

Citation: K.T K. Anandapandian, et al (2014). Optimization Of Mycelial Growth And Exopolysaccharide Production By *Calocybe Indica* Using Response Surface Methodology. *J. of Advancement in Medical and Life Sciences*. V1I3. DOI: 10.15297/JALS.V1I3.05

Copyright: © 2014 K.T K. Anandapandian. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.